

A Scoping Systematic Review of Mathematics and Statistics Support Evaluation Literature: Lessons Learnt

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Individual studies have demonstrated that mathematics and statistics support (MSS) provide academic and social benefits to students. However, results from individual studies can not necessarily be generalised. Systematic reviews are an important next step in the evolution of MSS research as they allow for findings from many studies to be combined and analysed. In this paper, the authors reflect on a recent scoping systematic review that they conducted and discuss what lessons can be learnt from it for planning and aiding future MSS research. For example, the authors propose the use of consistent terminology in MSS research, and a greater awareness of international MSS research.

Background

Lawson et al. (2003, p.9) consider mathematics and statistics support (MSS) as support ‘offered to students (not necessarily of mathematics) which is in addition to their regular programme of teaching through lectures, tutorials, seminars, problems, classes, personal tutorials, etc.’. This may be, for example, mathematics support centres, bridging courses, and workshops. Individual studies (Matthews et al., 2013) indicate that MSS assists students academically and socially. Building on Matthews et al. (2013) and the broader overview of MSS from Lawson et al. (2020), and in order to gain a deeper insight into how diverse types of MSS resources are being evaluated and whether they benefit students, the authors have conducted a scoping systematic literature review (Mullen et al., 2023).

Systematic reviews are an important next step in the evolution of MSS research as they allow for findings from many studies to be combined and analysed. Drawing on the hierarchy of evidence pyramid (NSW Government, 2020), systematic reviews and meta-analyses provide the strongest evidence and lowest bias for a research question as they are a formal process that draw on multiple studies as sources of evidence for their results. However, they can only be undertaken once a sufficient level of primary studies has been conducted. A scoping review, one type of systematic review, usually predates a full systematic review or meta-analysis. Scoping reviews ‘may examine the extent (that is, size), range (variety), and nature (characteristics) of the evidence on a topic or question; determine the value of undertaking a systematic review; summarise findings from a body of knowledge that is heterogeneous in methods or discipline; or identify gaps in the literature to aid the planning and commissioning of future research’ (Tricco et al., 2018, p.1).

When developing the protocol for the scoping review in question (Mullen et al., 2022), the authors discussed the approach to identifying MSS research, the eligibility criteria for including studies, and what general aspects of research would be useful for future researchers to know, e.g., funding sources. The scoping review has identified considerable variation in

MSS literature e.g., in the level of description of the MSS provided, in the reporting of the study design, and the evaluation approaches undertaken. This paper focuses on the description by Tricco et al. (2018) of scoping reviews as a way of aiding the planning and commissioning of future research. Therefore, this paper aims to present the authors' reflections on the identification of, and the methodological description provided by, MSS research.

Methodology

Studies were included in the scoping review if they met the following criteria during screening: a) published in English from 1st January 2000, b) the MSS provision was formally organised, optional for students and based within a higher education institution, c) studies included evaluation of the impact of MSS on students using either statistical methods or qualitative analysis. The scoping review included the following stages (Mullen et al., 2023):

1. Identification: Relevant studies were retrieved from pre-selected databases (ACM Digital Library, Australian Educational Database, Eric, PsychInfo, Scopus and Web of Science) using a pre-defined search string. The search string combined terms/synonyms for higher education and MSS (see Mullen et al., 2022), and returned studies where these words appeared in the study's title, abstract or keywords. The database search identified 3,009 records (including 1,314 duplicate records). Additional relevant pre-selected sources (MSS websites, reference lists of relevant studies, conference proceedings, MSOR Connections etc.) were searched and 189 further studies identified.
2. Round 1 Screening: Titles and abstracts of the database studies (n=1,695 with duplicate records removed) were screened to check if they met the eligibility criteria. In total, 169 met the criteria.
3. Round 2 Screening: Between the database search and additional sources, 349 relevant studies were found (full text) and screened (based on the full text). Subsequently, 149 studies were included in the scoping review.
4. Data Extraction: Pre-defined data items were extracted from each study.
5. Dissemination: Reporting of the scoping systematic review.

Descriptive statistics and summaries of the studies (for example, types of data collected, location of the institutions providing MSS, number of studies that received funding, and ethical approval status) are included in Mullen et al. (2023). This symposium paper reflects on the lessons learnt by the authors when undertaking the scoping review.

Results and Discussion

Identification of Mathematics and Statistics Support Research

In what ways is MSS beneficial for students? Systematics reviews can provide answers to questions such as this by drawing on multiple sources of evidence through a formal process, and therefore reducing bias in the answer. However, an essential part of this process is identifying the sources of evidence to draw on in the systematic review. The main approach is to create a search string, which is informed by the research question(s) and use the search string on different databases. A secondary search can also be conducted to draw on extra sources (which are generally identified using discipline knowledge).

Considering the main approach, studies need to be identifiable through matching terms in the search string to terms in their abstracts, keywords, and titles. This emphasises the importance of consistent and clear terminology in MSS research. The third author used their international contacts to identify different terms that are used for MSS e.g., learning assistance centre, calculus centre, and mathematics tutoring. It is likely that some terms used for MSS were not identified for the scoping review (Mullen et al., 2022). The authors propose that a series of keywords, which could be used internationally, may be established to make identification easier. In addition, a second consideration is that studies must be located on the pre-selected databases for them to be identifiable. For example, the Web of Science, one database that was used for the scoping review, proved not to contain all sources of MSS literature. The editors of Web of Science decide which journals, books and conference proceedings are included on it. While new sources can be submitted for consideration for inclusion, the editors decide based on a set of quality criteria what is included. For example, for a journal (and hence the journal's articles) to be included, the journal must have a registered ISSN, have a peer review policy, have a defined publication frequency, be transparent in their ethical requirements for authors, have stable citation activity etc. Some systematic reviews will only search databases as it ensures the literature meets these criteria.

The secondary search is an effective way of including additional sources of evidence and broadening the sources of evidence to other scholarly outputs (e.g., conference proceedings, websites, and reports). Using their discipline knowledge, and drawing on colleagues' knowledge, the authors identified additional sources of information (e.g., Sigma (UK) Network for Excellence in Mathematics and Statistics Support website, references from Matthews et al. (2013) and Lawson et al. (2020), and Southern Hemisphere Conference on the Teaching and Learning of Undergraduate Mathematics (Delta) proceedings). The largest source of additional studies for screening came from MSOR Connections (n=101). It is likely that some international sources were missed; particularly from countries where English is not the first language. It would benefit future systematic reviews on MSS if sources of MSS research are known internationally and studies are open access.

Eligibility Criteria

Which studies are included in a systematic review will also be impacted by the eligibility criteria. For example, following extended discussions concerning the diverse types of MSS, the authors chose to include only studies where the MSS was formally organised and had voluntary engagement by students. In one case a study was excluded as the support, a workshop on maths anxiety, was mandatory for all incoming students. The eligibility criteria were kept quite broad for the scoping systematic review (Mullen et al., 2023) as the purpose of scoping reviews are to identify gaps in the literature and provide a broader overview of the research area (Tricco et al., 2018). Full-systematic reviews tend to have more stringent eligibility criteria as they are trying to answer specific research questions. Common eligibility criteria for systematic reviews may be a minimum sample size, a specific study type (quantitative or qualitative) or design (e.g., interviews, questionnaires, third-person reporting, pre- and post-analysis), specific demographics (based on age, gender, educational level etc.),

location of study, or evaluation of specific measures (e.g., retention and confidence constructs). During Round 2 Screening of the scoping review, the authors discussed how some studies provided less methodological detail. Subsequently, the categories of different data items to be extracted from the studies were adapted. For example, as some studies did not explicitly state the study design, a new category of ‘not specified’ was created. An alternative approach, used by (scoping) systematic reviews, when methodological information is not stated explicitly, would be to exclude these studies. Similarly, it might be that the systematic review is examining a specific type of MSS support (e.g., drop-in maths support centre) and a study where the support is not described in sufficient detail (e.g., described as a maths support centre only) would be excluded even though the study is relevant for the review.

Conclusion

While systematic reviews are considered as a rigorous approach to synthesising the research on a topic, the authors hope this paper highlights the subjective nature of them and the importance of establishing a protocol for them which has been discussed in detail. To move forward with MSS research and evaluation, the authors propose that MSS research uses consistent terminology and explicitly states the methodology being used, and that there is increased awareness of MSS research internationally.

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